

A SCOPING REVIEW OF AI LITERACY:

Implications for governance
and public policy

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The wordmark for Canada, with the letters "Canada" in a black, serif font. A small Canadian flag is positioned above the letter "a".

Canada

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background

As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly embedded in public infrastructure and everyday life, there is an urgent need for meaningful public understanding of and engagement in its governance and regulation. While AI technology itself is not new, the conditions under which it operates, and the scale at which it is deployed, have shifted significantly (Quan-Haase, 2020). While the integration of AI into work settings is seen as improving efficiency (Jethra et al., 2025; Kassa & Ketema, 2025), growing evidence shows that if left unchecked, AI systems reinforce systemic biases and disproportionately harm marginalized communities (Iloanusi & Chun, 2024; O'Neil, 2017). This potential for a range of negative social consequences, in particular consequences affecting vulnerable individuals and communities, necessitates new approaches to AI governance and regulation. For individuals and communities to engage deeply with the role of AI in society, it is necessary that they join the conversation, providing input into its development, use, and long-term implementation. But how to ensure meaningful, and inclusive consultation is still unclear and has no straightforward solution. The problem is urgent because if AI remains without critical safeguards, this will deepen social inequalities, producing a new AI divide where those with fewer resources, skills, or access to AI technologies are further excluded from social, economic, and civic participation (Coeckelbergh, 2025). Scholars and practitioners are calling for the development of AI literacy as an integral part of digital equity and inclusion (Cotter & Reisdorf, 2020). By strengthening AI literacy and engaging in capacity building across a range of diverse communities, we can create a pathway for deeper public engagement (Delgado, et al., 2023). This will lower many of the barriers to consultation, such as making technical and specialized language more accessible, creating more transparency around the black-box nature of AI, and providing opportunities for engagement with AI technologies in real-life contexts. However, the concept of AI literacy is not yet well understood and key studies on the topic are dispersed across disciplines, with little attempt for integration. Moreover, our understanding of how to develop and sustain AI literacy in various populations in light of rapid technological change remains limited.

The Issue

Canada and the UK are racing ahead in AI innovations, yet this trajectory of global leadership conceals a troubling vulnerability: the public is underprepared to critically understand and engage with the AI ecosystem, despite the growing influence of AI on everyday life. At the same time, AI literacy research is emerging while the concept is simultaneously being defined, with research practices and conceptualizations mutually shaping one another. How AI literacy is framed now will shape public engagement with the AI ecosystem into the future. This creates an urgent need to ensure that AI literacy is not narrowly reduced to technical competencies alone, but instead framed in ways that strengthen public understanding, participation, and agency in an increasingly AI-mediated society.

The primary research objective is to provide a comprehensive overview of approaches to studying AI literacy through a scoping review, with the following three specific objectives:

- (1) to understand the range of definitions of AI literacy, the types of definitions, and potential gaps;
- (2) to evaluate methodological approaches; and
- (3) to examine how the social context is taken into consideration in studies of AI literacy.

Methodology

This project is a scoping review of studies on AI literacy published globally between 2015 and 2024. We used the “PRISMA Extension for Scoping Review” checklist and the PRISMA flow chart to guide the review process. We also followed the widely used scoping review framework developed by Arksey and O’Malley, which helped structure each stage of our review. We started with identifying key resources on the topic of AI literacy, reading them carefully, and extracting a list of the key terms utilized in the titles, abstracts, and full texts. Additionally, we checked the keywords used in these publications and the associated database thesaurus of subject headings. Based on our testing protocol, seven databases were selected for our final search, containing resources on the topics of technology, communications, and learning. In total, 129 studies were included in the review based on our inclusion and exclusion screening process. We used thematic analysis to identify key patterns across the studies. A coding scheme with six themes was developed and tested in two rounds of team coding, reaching 90% agreement between researchers. The final coding guide was then used to review all remaining studies. Examples from the studies are included throughout the report and the dataset is available as an open access resource for future studies (Appendix).

Results

The results show that the field is fragmented, with a wide application of terms, methods, and underlying assumptions used across studies and contexts. Six main themes were identified: 1) definitions, 2) methods, 3) purpose, 4) social context, 5) discipline and setting, and 6) outcome.

The most common terms used are AI literacy, algorithm awareness, and algorithm literacy. Most studies focus on technical knowledge and individual skill development, with much less attention given to how the social context of individuals influences AI literacy acquisition. About half of the studies use quantitative methods such as surveys, while fewer studies used qualitative or mixed methods approaches. Preliminary findings demonstrate that measurement practices are marked by an overreliance on self-report instruments and a lack of demonstrated or in-context assessment of AI literacy. The most common research goal is assessing a person’s knowledge or misconceptions about AI.

Surprisingly, education is the leading field studying AI literacy, with a focus on assessing and strengthening AI competencies of learners and/or instructors. Many studies include basic demographic data, but few use the demographic data to understand the role of social and economic inequalities in the acquisition of AI literacy. Learning-oriented outcomes are the most common, with studies primarily focusing on improving awareness, understanding, and skills among the studied populations; while technological and economic outcomes are rarely the focus of studies. Recommendations across the literature reflect a similar pattern. Most studies call for further research or an expanded research scope. Policy-orientated recommendations are rare, with only limited engagement with governance, regulatory, or systemic interventions. This suggests that AI literacy research remains largely focused on individual capacity, rather than the broader systems shaping the AI ecosystem

Key Message

This gap between promise and practice exposes an urgent need for a more socially grounded understanding of AI literacy. We identify critical AI literacy as a key dimension that emphasizes informed decision-making, critical engagement, and resistance to technological coercion by taking an agency-driven approach. Across our review, broader patterns reveal systemic barriers to developing stronger critical AI literacy, limiting the possibility for coordinated, fair, and trusted approach to AI governance.

BACKGROUND

The rise and relevance of AI literacy

Artificial intelligence (AI) is embedded in the structures that shape everyday life, from public services and education, to employment, healthcare, and civic participation. AI most commonly refers to a computer system capable of completing complex tasks by recognizing and replicating patterns in data (Government of Canada, 2026). However, AI does not operate in isolation. It exists within a complex network that includes industry, policymakers, technical experts, workers, public institutions, the data and infrastructure that enable AI integration, and, most critically, the public users and communities who experience its impacts.

Throughout this report, our team intentionally adopts the term *AI ecosystem* to reflect our positional understanding of AI as a sociotechnical system shaped by symbiotic social, economic, and political, and technological relationships (Livingstone, 2004; Pedreschi et al., 2023). We are further informed by Kate Crawford's argument that AI is neither artificial, nor inherently intelligent, but instead, "both embodied and material, made from natural resources, fuel, human labor, infrastructures, logistics, histories, and classifications" (2021, p. 8). We understand the AI ecosystem as a shared responsibility that requires the meaningful inclusion of the public in AI development, use, and governance. As AI ecosystems expand, so too does the expectation that individuals can navigate within and critically respond to them. In response, AI literacy has gained traction as a key concept for examining how individuals and communities understand, engage with, and make sense of AI (Carolus et al., 2023; Long & Magerko, 2020; Ng et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2024).

While AI literacy is increasingly recognized as a distinct domain, there is limited clarity on how to conceptualize it. Much of the current literature focuses on measuring AI literacy through competency-based models (Lintner, 2024). While these approaches offer useful benchmarks, they risk narrowing the concept prematurely by failing to capture the complexity of how individuals encounter, interpret, and integrate AI tools within their everyday contexts. Indeed, scholars and practitioners are calling for the development of AI literacy as an integral part of digital equity and inclusion, given that societies and governments are increasingly reliant on AI integration (Cotter & Reisdorf, 2020). AI literacy becomes particularly relevant in an economy where an AI skillset is an expected part of many jobs of the future (Future Skills Centre, 2024).

Early insights from research on algorithmic literacy have been instructive in shaping the field. Studies demonstrate that limited public awareness of algorithmic systems constrains the development of meaningful AI literacy (Gran et al., 2021). This challenge is compounded by the opaque and often "black-box" nature of AI systems, which makes it difficult to discern how these systems make decisions or to understand their broader social and economic implications (Burrell, 2016; O'Neil, 2017; Petrovčič et al., 2024). While the integration of AI into work settings is seen as improving efficiency (Jethra et al., 2025; Kassa & Ketema, 2025), growing evidence shows that if left unchecked, AI systems reinforce systemic biases and disproportionately harm marginalized communities (Iloanusi & Chun, 2024; O'Neil, 2017). Predictive models used in hiring, credit scoring, policing, and education often rely on historical data that reflects existing inequalities (O'Neil, 2017). When these models are deployed at scale, they can systematically disadvantage already marginalized populations while appearing neutral or objective. Similarly, research on facial recognition technologies demonstrates that widely used facial recognition systems exhibit significantly higher error rates for darker-skinned individuals, particularly women, revealing how algorithmic systems can differentially fail across populations and amplify existing systemic, intersectional, and structural biases (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018).

As van Deursen and Mossberger (2018) highlight, these dynamics have uneven effects, disproportionately impacting individuals with differing levels of digital access, skills, and institutional support to understand the layers of AI integration. This gap between promise and practice exposes an urgent need for a more socially-grounded understanding of AI literacy. As a result, we identify critical AI literacy as a key dimension that includes informed decision-making, critical engagement, and resistance to technological coercion by taking an agency-driven approach (Maeda et al., 2025; Veldhuis, 2024). It must equip individuals and communities not only to use AI tools, but to understand how they shape outcomes, to critically interrogate their impacts, and to challenge or refuse their adoption where necessary.

Evolving conceptualizations of literacies

The term AI literacy emerges from broader definitions of literacy, traditionally understood as the ability to read, write, and comprehend (McBride, 2015). This term has been extended to new literacies (Leu et al., 2017), such as media, digital, information, computer, and IT literacy (Kong et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2021). In this context, the term literacy is used primarily as a synonym for a competency or skill. Digital (or computer) literacy is defined as the set of skills that enables a user to effectively operate software tools, or perform basic information retrieval tasks (Bawden, 2008; Helsper, 2011). This reflects a functional definition: it specifies the basic skills that are required to undertake particular tasks (Buckingham, 2015).

Grounded in earlier media theory, including Marshall McLuhan's emphasis on how media environments shape human perceptions and experiences (McLuhan et al., 2001), media literacy developed as a critical framework of not just competencies, but for analysing and creating media content. Beginning in the 1990s and accelerating into the early 2000s, media literacy became increasingly associated with digital and networked media. In this shifting context, Sonia Livingstone (2004) outlined four widely adopted components of media literacy: 1) the ability to access, 2) analyse, 3) evaluate, and 4) create content across a variety of contexts. These components contributed to the skills-based approach to literacy that can be seen in other forms of digital literacy. Underpinning this is the assumption that, in a knowledge-based society, all members of society must be digitally literate and possess basic skills or competencies in order to participate in civic life (Bawden, 2008; van Laar et al., 2017). However, in response, Livingstone (2004) cautions that a static and traditional skills-based approach is insufficient on its own, arguing that "we must ask how literacy changes – and becomes plural – as the technology changes" (p. 7).

Gilster (1997) introduces the idea that digital literacy goes beyond mere technical proficiency to encompass the ability to engage critically and creatively with the digital world. Livingstone (2004) further highlights how definitions of media literacy need to foreground where people are positioned, "not merely as selective, receptive, and accepting but also as participating, critical; in short, not merely as consumers but also as citizens" (p. 11). This underlines the tension in differing definitions of literacy, from ones where it is treated as a functional set of skills to ones that are increasingly part of public agency, and a means for people to participate in society and governance.

Yet even the language of literacy carries ideological implications. It is important to recognize that AI literacy is not a fixed nor settled concept. Earlier debates about digital literacy carried the same cautions. Wysocki and Johnson-Eiola (1999) warned in the age of nascent computer literacy that too much is hidden by the word literacy: assuming a lack of literacy misattributes systemic oppression to individual deficits. As Livingstone (2004) conceptualizes it, literacy cannot be reduced to narrow skill-sets, but instead reflects a "historically and culturally conditioned relationship" among systems of knowledge, culture, and values, the uneven distribution of skills between social contexts, and the institutional management of power tied to access and knowledge (p.11). If the term literacy is to continue to guide policy and practice, as it has throughout these periods of technological change, it must be used intentionally, with critical attention to the kind of assumptions, responsibilities, and outcomes it produces.

Digital inequities and the emerging “AI divide”

The concept of the digital divide first emerged in the 1990s as governments and scholars grappled with stark disparities in access to computers and the internet (Gonzales, 2016; Parayil, 2005). Initially framed as a binary gap between the “haves” and “have nots”, it quickly expanded to include what online activities were available to individuals and the benefits they derived from them (Jaeger et al, 2012; Lybeck et al., 2023; Robinson et al., 2015; Stevenson, 2009).

This insight gave rise to more layered models of digital inequality that emphasized the intersection of skills, participation, and outcomes (Jaeger et al., 2012; van Dijk, 2020). Artificial intelligence adds a new and urgent dimension to this landscape and is aptly described as the “AI divide”. Carter et al. (2020) were among the first to systematically articulate this concept, and argue that inequalities in access, skills, and outcomes would not only be reproduced but intensified, as AI systems became embedded in everyday life. Building on this foundation, Mohammed et al. (2024) reconceptualized the AI divide as a multi-faceted problem with four interlinked dimensions: 1) accessible AI technologies, 2) digital and algorithmic literacy, 3) unbiased AI outcomes, and 4) effective regulation. Their framework expands the conversation from individual access and use, towards systemic questions of governance, fairness, and democratic participation.

Without this shift, the AI divide risks a divided landscape: those with education, income, and technical expertise benefit, while marginalized groups face double exclusion not only from digital economies but from civic decision-making itself. The current discourse on AI literacy remains focused on bridging the AI divide through the acquisition of technical skills and awareness (Bećirović et al., 2025). If people cannot meaningfully engage with or contest the systems increasingly shaping their lives, they risk becoming what R. David Lankes warns could be “a class [of people] used by algorithms” rather than empowered participants shaping them (Lankes, as quoted in Rainie & Anderson, 2017, p. 76). Furthermore, research on digital inclusion suggests that gaps in AI literacy have the potential to not merely replicate existing inequalities; they could also compound them across intersecting lines of income, education, race, disability, and other forms of social stratification (Helsper, 2021; Robinson et al., 2015; van Deursen et al., 2017). When those communities already marginalized by digital inequalities are also excluded from understanding AI or shaping its accountabilities, the result is a widening divide in civic participation. This makes AI literacy a pressing social and civic justice concern (Duarte & Garcia, 2024; Gran et al., 2021).

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Why this matters

Our team is drawn to this moment of emergence, where AI literacy is still fluid and contested, creating an opportunity to reimagine more democratic relationships with technology.

Canada and the UK are racing ahead in AI innovations, yet this trajectory of global leadership conceals a troubling vulnerability: the public is underprepared to critically understand and engage with the AI ecosystem, despite the growing influence of AI on everyday life. At the same time, AI literacy research is emerging while the concept is simultaneously being defined, with research practices and conceptualizations mutually shaping one another. How AI literacy is framed now will shape public engagement with the AI ecosystem into the future. This creates an urgent need to ensure that AI literacy is not narrowly reduced to technical competencies alone, but instead framed in ways that strengthen public understanding, participation, and agency in an increasingly AI-mediated society.

OBJECTIVES

The key research objective is to provide a comprehensive overview of the range of approaches to the study of AI literacy. The scoping review has three specific objectives:

To understand how AI literacy is defined and understood across different contexts

To evaluate the research methods used to study AI literacy across different contexts

To examine the ways that social-economic factors are considered in AI literacy research

Bringing together findings across disciplines, this scoping review identifies key gaps, areas of emerging consensus, and provides evidence to guide more coordinated and equitable approaches to AI governance.

METHODS

A scoping approach to an emerging field

We conducted a scoping review to provide a comprehensive overview of the range of approaches used to study AI literacy as well as to identify gaps in the existing literature with the aim of proposing future avenues of research. While systematic reviews address narrowly defined research questions, scoping reviews allow for the exploration of emerging fields where concepts, theories, and methods are still developing and are not as yet well understood nor fully formulated (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Levac et al., 2010). With AI literacy rapidly emerging as a central concept of interest to academia, non-profit organizations, and governments, a scoping review was selected to initiate a deeper analysis into this emerging interdisciplinary field.

To ensure a transparent and rigorous approach, we relied on the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist (Tricco, et al., 2018) and included as well the 2020 PRISMA flow chart (Page, et al. 2021). We followed the process for scoping reviews proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005) to obtain guidance in the process from the formulation of the research objectives to the identification of key resources, to the final stage of report writing. The first step in Arksey and O'Malley's (2005) framework is the identification of the research objectives. The following three research objectives guided the scoping review process: (1) to understand the range of definitions of AI literacy, the types of definitions, and potential conceptual gaps; (2) to evaluate methodological approaches; and (3) to examine how the social context (e.g., social inequality, technological access) is taken into consideration in studies of AI literacy.

OUR ITERATIVE SCOPING REVIEW PROCESS

Adapted from Arksey and O'Malley (2005)

Search Strategy

Following Arksey and O'Malley's (2005) framework, step 2 consists of the formulation of a search string, which is a complex and iterative process. We started with identifying key resources on the topic of AI literacy, reading them carefully and extracting a list of the key terms utilized in the title, abstract, and full text. Additionally, we checked the keywords used in these publications and the associated database thesaurus of subject headings. The initial keywords resulted in a search query, which was tested and further refined through team discussions and iterative testing in various databases. As one of the team members has a master's degree in library and information science, their expertise in search query development and database searches supported the refinement of the search string. We extensively tested various combinations of search terms for efficacy before arriving at the final search string.

("algorithm literacy" OR "algorithm* awareness" OR "artificial intelligence literacy" OR "artificial intelligence awareness")*

and

(study OR test OR interview OR questionnaire OR experiment* OR qualitative OR quantitative)*

Using this search query consistently across all databases, we first searched several databases from June 12 to June 30, 2024. Each database was tested for relevance using a search string of “literacy” AND “artificial intelligence” to first assess if they would yield viable results. Based on the testing, seven databases were selected for our final search containing resources on the topics of technology, communications, and learning. The selected 7 databases were: Academic Search Ultimate, ACM Digital Library, ERIC, IEEE Xplore, Science Direct, Scopus, and Web of Science. As described below, Google Scholar was later added for final check.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Step 3 according to Arksey and O’Malley’s (2005) framework consists of the identification of key resources. Given the recency of the topic, we extracted relevant sources published between 2015 and 2024. The search query yielded 609 resources across 7 databases. Google Scholar was excluded in this first round of searches, as it indexes all publications on the internet including white papers. Following the PRISMA flow chart, the next step was screening each of the identified resources. Central to the screening process is the articulation of a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

| EXCLUSION CRITERIA |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focus on AI or algorithmic literacy or AI awareness• Qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods research• Review methods such as systematic, scoping, or integrative• Educational studies that measure AI or algorithmic awareness, knowledge, or skill set (e.g., intervention, pre- and post-test design as part of a learning session) | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Unrelated aspects of AI such as technical briefs or descriptions of specific applications• Studies focused on recommendations without an empirical component such as a policy briefs or white papers• Short sources such as proceeding introductions, extended abstracts, or similar brief work• Duplicates |

Three team members independently checked each resource taking into consideration the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Team members also met to discuss the criteria to guarantee its consistent application. A first screening based on title and abstract removed 336 entries from the initial 609 identified in the search and identified 273 resources for extraction. Following the extraction, each resource was closely screened for a second time using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Through this close screening, duplicates and papers that addressed unrelated aspects of AI were removed. This final screening yielded a sample of 117 studies. Next, we conducted a search on Google Scholar using the same search string, and identified 110 resources, which were all screened using the inclusion/exclusion criteria, yielding a total of 12 new inclusions. The final sample of literature included for analysis was 129 studies.

PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram for the Identification of Studies on AI Literacy

Source: Page MJ, et al. BMJ 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.
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Data Analysis

The data analysis stage comprised the development of codes and themes following the procedures of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A codebook with 6 themes was developed for this review based on a close reading of key resources identified. The first round of coding focused on 15 papers to test the preliminary coding scheme and to establish intercoder reliability. After a first round of coding and a team meeting to discuss discrepancies, an additional 15 resources were coded in a second round, reaching 90% agreement. The team then used the final coding scheme to code all remaining resources. Throughout the report, we refer to studies from the dataset to exemplify key points. Each study is referred to following APA reference style using first author and year of publication, adding the ID for each resource given in the dataset. This dataset is available in Appendix A and as a downloadable open access resource AT

RESULTS

By mapping how AI literacy and related terms are conceptualized, studied, and evaluated across disciplines, this review identifies dominant themes and notable gaps in existing research. The findings reveal substantial variation in terminology, measurement approaches, and underlying assumptions about users, technologies, and social contexts, reflecting the rapidly evolving nature of the AI ecosystem. We report the findings around the six themes identified in the thematic analysis and also identify research gaps. The six themes are not exclusive of one another, as concepts, methods, and assumptions can intersect.

Six Main Themes Identified in the AI Literacy Literature

Definitions

Examines how AI literacy and related terms are conceptualized, including explicit definitions and alternative terminology used to describe these concepts across disciplines.

Methods

Captures the methodological approaches—qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods—employed to evaluate AI literacy, including assessment of measurement instruments.

Purpose

Identifies the core research questions, objectives, and phenomena examined or explored in each resource.

Social Context

Analyzes the social context in which AI literacy is set, including participants' demographics, socioeconomic factors, geographical location, technological access, and theoretical frameworks applied. This captures both examined social factors as well as overlooked factors.

Discipline & Setting

Categorizes the academic field or interdisciplinary approaches within which each resource is situated.

Outcomes and Recommendations

Evaluates the empirical basis of conclusions, distinguishing between data-driven findings and author interpretations, whilst documenting and examining specific outcomes and recommendations.

1. Definitions of AI Literacy

Our analysis reveals significant divergence in how the terms AI literacy, algorithmic literacy, and other related terms are utilized. To illustrate this divergence, the graph below presents what terms were most frequently utilized in the studies examined: AI literacy (47%), algorithm awareness (24%), and algorithm literacy (14%). AI awareness is rarely used, with only 2% of studies using this term. About 13% of studies use other terms. This suggests that AI and algorithm are, in some cases, treated as interchangeable, but also domain specific. AI literacy refers to a broader type of literacy that encompasses a range of AI systems and understandings, while algorithm refers to a subset of AI systems, namely automated sets of rules that users encounter on the web and social media. Although the two are closely related, treating them as interchangeable obscures important distinctions in scale, function, and impact.

We found in the scoping review that how these terms are used varies by disciplinary context. AI literacy is most commonly used in the fields of education and computer science, where studies frequently focus on AI competencies such as AI knowledge, AI skills, and the responsible use of AI systems. It is referred to far less frequently as a term in the fields of social sciences, communication, and media studies. By contrast, algorithm awareness or algorithm literacy are the dominant terms within those fields, and they are rarely utilized in education-focused studies. This suggests that there is a fragmentation in the use of these related terms by discipline, where different terms have slightly different meaning and function between each field. This finding is important because scholars, practitioners, and policymakers searching for relevant resources need to utilize at least three keywords to identify relevant materials across disciplines: AI literacy, algorithm awareness, and algorithm literacy. An additional important consideration based on this finding is that when scholars refer to AI literacy or related terminology, they may refer to a specific meaning of the term, one that is grounded in disciplinary understandings. This can make interdisciplinary work more challenging, as there is a disconnect when communicating (Quan-Haase, et. al., 2022).

While AI literacy is the most commonly used term by far, with 47% of studies using this term, its use is inconsistent across sources, and, at times, within individual studies. Our analysis shows significant internal inconsistency in the use of AI literacy related terminology. A small, but notable, subset of studies (11, 9%) change which terminology they use throughout the paper; for example, they utilize one term in their introduction but then switch to a different term in their findings and/or discussion sections, without distinguishing a difference between them. For example, Kasinidou et al. (2023, ID_023) discuss AI literacy in the abstract and introduction of their study on creating a distance AI learning course, as well as list it as one of the study's keywords, but later switch to primarily describing how students were aware of AI and the attitudes they had toward the technology in the discussion section.

Distribution of primary terminology in AI literacy studies

The findings demonstrate that different terms signal different disciplinary orientations and assumptions about how to approach the study of AI and AI literacy, with some focusing on algorithms specifically and others more generally on AI as a broader concept. This suggests that not only are the definitions of the fundamental concept of AI vague, but there is also inconsistency of terminology use, where authors are not using terms consistently throughout a single resource, creating conceptual misalignments. We did not see system or platform-specific terms used as frequently in the resources to refer to AI, such as generative AI, Large Language Models (LLM), ChatGPT, or chatbots.

Preliminary thematic analysis further suggests that definitions cluster into four categories, with a fifth category capturing more specialized or domain-specific models. These categories are:

1. **Competency-based approaches:** focused on skills, knowledge, and ethical use of AI.
2. **Awareness-oriented approaches:** centered on recognizing the presence and influence of AI or algorithms on everyday life.
3. **Technical approaches:** emphasizing programming, system design, or operational understandings.
4. **Critical or sociotechnical approaches:** focused on power, inequality, governance, and resistance.
5. **Specialized frameworks:** tailored to particular professions, sectors, or use cases.

The co-existence of these approaches within the same corpus of literature contributes to the widespread conceptual fragmentation. Studies that appear aligned at the level of terminology, may, in practice, be grounded in different assumptions. Across these definitional approaches, several critical limitations recur. Most definitions implicitly assume voluntary engagement with AI ecosystems and position individuals as autonomous agents who can choose how and when to interact with algorithmic technologies. AI literacy is framed as something individuals develop to better navigate technological encounters. This assumption is particularly problematic in contexts where AI ecosystems are encountered involuntarily or coercively, such as within the criminal justice, healthcare, or social services systems, where individuals may have little ability to opt out, contest decisions, or meaningfully influence system design. The dominant emphasis on individual skill development further risks deflecting attention away from collective resistance strategies, structural reforms, and institutional accountability.

These limitations are evident in the distribution of studies across the categories. Of the total 129 studies reviewed, 33% (43) focus on cultivating awareness or understandings of AI or algorithmic systems without addressing a user's holistic decision-making capacities – what we conceptualize as user-agency (Maeda et. al, 2025). Of the subset of studies that do engage with agency, it is most often equated with performance, defined as the maximization of one's ability to wield AI tools. Capacity for refusal, non-use, or resistance are largely absent, with non-participation frequently framed as a deficiency in competency or a form of AI illiteracy, rather than as an informed or strategic choice.

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Additional problems with how AI ecosystems are being described to participants are also discovered in our data. When examining how AI was discussed in each study, the majority of authors (100, 78%) describe AI or algorithms in a general, non-specific way. Specific terminology of the type of AI being studied, such as natural language processing and computer vision, is limited (17, 13%). For example, Tanksley's (2024, ID_002) findings, which relate to a high school AI class, discuss how AI as a general concept influences students in the classroom. In Tanksley's study, the term AI is treated as a generic entity that has reference to an abstract concept. It is only in the findings that specific systems are referenced, when a participant quote refers to ChatGPT. In our dataset, we found that participants were often asked about their literacy in relation to AI, where AI was left as an abstract and self-explanatory term. This demonstrates that AI remains an ambiguous concept, and existing literacy scales may not be capturing the nuance of different AI literacies, which can range from interactions with customer service chatbots to complex AI processes embedded within infrastructural systems.

This lack of conceptual consistency not only in terminology, but also in the corresponding assumptions of what AI is and encompasses, means that AI literacy studies are not being undertaken in a systematic manner, and therefore findings across studies are typically not comparable. Without greater clarity and stronger alignment between definitions, efforts to assess or advance AI literacy will remain difficult, as we cannot effectively compare, scale, or translate findings into policy and practice. The use of terminology can change over time as the field starts consolidating, and we expect the diversity of terms to increase further.

We recommend a follow-up scoping review in 3 years to re-examine the use of terminology and the evolution of discipline-specific uses.

2. Research methods in AI literacy research

Results indicate substantial methodological diversity across the scoping review, though quantitative approaches are most common. About half of the reviewed studies (62) employ quantitative methods, frequently relying on surveys, self-report scales, attitude measures, or structured performance assessments. These approaches often measure participants' knowledge, confidence, awareness, or perceived competence in relation to AI ecosystems. This demonstrates a need to quantify the AI literacy levels amongst different groups to determine benchmarks and develop interventions with the aim of strengthening AI literacy.

We found that 31% of studies (40) use qualitative methods, including interviews, open-ended inquiry, and ethnographies. These studies are more likely to explore how participants understand AI in context, make meaning of algorithmic systems, or reflect on broader social and ethical implications. Just over 20% of studies (27) adopt a mixed methods design, combining surveys or scales with interviews, scenario-based tasks, or performance measures. These approaches aim to capture both measurable outcomes and more nuanced experiences or interpretations. The aim of mixed methods approaches is to show how people are interpreting AI in the context of their everyday lives and what meaning they are giving to AI as it evolves. It also facilitates deeper conversations around what is working in terms of their use of AI and where they need more capacity building.

Research Methods in AI literacy studies

Quantitative Methods

- surveys
- self-report scales
- attitude measurements
- technical performance assessments

Mixed Methods

- surveys or scales AND:
- interviews
 - observation
 - scenario-based

Qualitative Methods

- interviews
- open-ended inquiries
- ethnographies

What each method captures

Quantitative

Knowledge, skills, & performance

Measures participants' knowledge, confidence, awareness, and perceived competence in relation to AI systems. These approaches help establish benchmarks across diverse groups and inform the design of interventions to strengthen AI literacy.

Mixed

Both measurement and meaning

Explores how participants understand and experience AI in their everyday lives, capturing the meaning they assign as AI technologies evolve. These approaches also open space for deeper reflection on what is working in practice and where additional support or capacity-building is needed.

Qualitative

Meaning, context, and critique

Captures how participants understand AI in context, make meaning of algorithmic systems, or reflect on social implications, including ethical, social, cultural, economic, and power-related dimensions. Relies heavily on both perception and experience, without benchmarks used for comparison.

← measurement / generalization

← integrative / nuanced

→ meaning-making / context-driven

To measure critical engagement with AI, a scaffolded set of AI literacy measures need to be developed and validated. Across the included literature, preliminary findings demonstrate that measurement practices are marked by an over-reliance on self-report instruments and a lack of demonstrated or in-context assessment of AI literacy. Most studies operationalize AI literacy through interviews, surveys, or questionnaires that capture a participant's perceived knowledge, confidence, or awareness rather than their ability to apply judgment, exercise agency, or respond to AI ecosystems in practice. This approach contributes to a persistent disconnect between theoretical definitions of AI literacy which gesture toward critical evaluation or ethical reasoning, and their operationalization. It also relies heavily on the public's self-perceptions of their AI literacy and researchers' assumptions about how that literacy manifests, without external benchmarks available for comparison. This calls for further qualitative inquiry or mixed methods approaches that can capture how individuals and communities are actually using and interacting with AI in the context of their everyday lives in the city or at work, home, and school.

Even when literacy frameworks indicate that they include an individual's capability to critically evaluate AI systems, measurement typically focuses on assessment accuracy or ecosystem comprehension, rather than on whether a participant interrogates power relations, institutional deployment, or broader social consequences. Approximately half of the studies in the dataset rely exclusively on quantitative methods, and within this subset, 39% (24 of 62) focus primarily on knowledge acquisition and misconceptions about AI systems. Mixed method approaches, most commonly combining surveys with interviews or observational components, tend to privilege awareness and understanding over critical application or evaluation.

Widely used self-report scales such as the AI Literacy Scale (AILS) (Wang et al., 2022, ID_092), the Algorithmic Media Content Awareness Scale (AMCA) (Zarouali, 2021, ID_083), and the General Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale (GAAIS) (Lipovec & Flogie, 2023, ID_058) further reinforce this pattern by emphasizing technical knowledge, functional awareness, and perceived competence.

While performance-based assessments such as concept inventories or practical application tasks are employed in some studies (e.g., Zhang et al., 2024, ID_047), they remain comparatively rare and are still generally more oriented towards technical proficiency rather than critical engagement or structural analysis. Contextual sensitivity also remains limited. Although a small number of domain-specific instruments have been developed for settings such as healthcare, education, or the workplace, most scales implicitly treat AI literacy as a universal construct, easily transferable across contexts and tools. Few measures account for cross-cultural variation, involuntary encounters with AI ecosystems, or structural inequalities that shape an individual's means to contest or refuse algorithmic decision-making. These methodological approaches narrow the scope of what is measured as AI literacy, reinforcing a model centered on individual skill while sidelining collective, contextual, and justice-oriented dimensions of engagement with AI.

Overall, the findings suggest that the field relies heavily on measurement tools centered on an individual's perception and self-reported evaluation, while fewer studies assess situated practice, longitudinal development, or collective dimensions of AI engagement. This imbalance narrows how AI literacy is understood and evaluated, reinforcing a predominantly individual and decontextualized understanding of competence and user-agency.

3. Purpose of study

To better understand how AI literacy and related terms are being operationalized in practice, studies were coded by their primary research purpose. In those cases where studies were interdisciplinary in nature, multiple codes were applied, with the most relevant purpose listed first. Coding studies in this way makes visible the underlying assumptions shaping how AI literacy is researched.

The scoping review reveals a strong emphasis on the development of assessment tools such as scales, surveys, and measures that can establish the AI literacy level of a population. Related to this is an emphasis on the creation of effective educational interventions. Often, the purpose of a study is practical in nature, with the aim of improving AI literacy within educational settings. While many literacy frameworks cited in the studies reference critical evaluation and reflection, this is often measured through accuracy, recognition, or awareness or knowledge of AI rather than through questions of AI governance, resistance, or institutional accountability. The scoping review shows that there is a need to expand the objectives of current studies to include more research questions focused on the role of AI literacy in governance and public engagement in AI policy.

We found that 39% of reviewed studies (50) focus on assessing AI literacy, examining participants' understanding, knowledge, or misconceptions of AI and related technologies, making this the most common research purpose. Combining these elements as a single code reflects that understanding and misunderstanding are co-constructive, offering a more holistic view of how participants make sense of AI ecosystems. These studies typically assess whether participants understand how AI systems function or hold mistaken beliefs about algorithms.

For example, Zarouali et. al (2021, ID_082) found that a significant proportion of the general population held multiple misconceptions about algorithms in media environments. While the authors' study engages with both theoretical and societal implications, and draws on the concept of algorithmic awareness, it ultimately relies on a quantitative approach to measure the presence and distribution of these misconceptions. For example, the authors found that 5 out of 10 participants believed that algorithms always operate neutrally and objectively, and thus, are free of bias. Similarly, 5 out of 10 participants believed that algorithms have the same level of critical reasoning and intelligence as humans. This study was able to demonstrate misconceptions in how people understand AI and thus provides clear guidance for educational interventions. However, because of the quantification, it does not engage in a deeper engagement with questions around AI ethics or limitations, nor how AI technologies intersect with social inequalities and biases.

A further 19% of studies (25) evaluate a classroom tool, curriculum modification, or teaching method for strengthening AI literacy, reflecting the field's strong grounding in educational interventions and instructional design. For example, Uygun et al. (2024, ID_121), employed the domain-specific Teachers' Artificial Intelligence Awareness Scale to assess a teacher's AI awareness level and examine how these vary across demographic factors such as age, education, and experience. The authors' aim is to use these findings to inform the development of targeted teacher training, interventions, and educational programs.

Around 16% of studies (21) aim to develop or validate a test or scale intended to measure a user's literacy, awareness, or related competencies, reinforcing the tendency to treat AI literacy as a construct to be quantified. However, some studies expand this framing to include critical dimensions. In Mattias et al. (2023, ID_127), AI literacy is defined to include the "critical use of AI applications by non-experts" (p. 1), and this is reflected in the study design through the inclusion of "critical appraisal" as an AI competency, alongside technical understanding and practical application. This suggests that how AI literacy is defined directly shapes what is measured, illustrating the concurrent formation of conceptualization of AI literacy and the research design used to examine it.

Approximately 10% of studies (13) examine a participant's online behaviour, including interactions with AI-driven systems such as recommender systems, search engines, or social media environments. Less than 10% of studies (10) focus primarily on how people use a specific technology or platform, examining engagement with particular AI tools or applications. Similarly, few studies have conducted systematic or substantial literature reviews, indicating that comparatively limited attention has been devoted to synthesizing the rapidly expanding evidence base.

These findings suggest that the priorities of current research continue to center assessment and measurement as well as instructional outcomes, while broader questions of lived experience, social context, and collective responses to AI ecosystems receive limited attention. By contrast, civil society initiatives such as Connected by Data and We and AI foreground these dimensions through work that combines research, public engagement, and community-grounded approaches (Connected by Data, 2023; We and AI, n.d.). Their work highlights a disconnect between what is currently prioritized within the academic field and the concerns being actively explored and addressed within community contexts.

4. Social Context

There were several factors analyzed related to the social context of each study, with the aim of understanding how authors consider these various factors in their understanding of AI literacy. A key goal of the analysis of social context is also the identification of research gaps. For example, the sub-code “external skillset” looks at how researchers considered the role of related skills such as digital skills, media literacy, and fact-checking skills when considering a person’s AI literacy.

We found a variety of social factors that were included in the studies, such as user familiarity with the platform/tool/technology being investigated (39, 30%), overall reading level or educational attainment (28, 22%), and the participant’s digital literacy skills (20, 16%). For example, Hwang et al. (2023, ID_129) took into consideration a participant’s ability to utilize AI systems in the design of their digital literacy scale. However, about a third of studies (38, 29%) did not consider the participant’s external skillset as a factor when assessing AI literacy. This finding suggests that AI literacy is not being conceptualized as related to or embedded in other types of literacy or technology skillsets, but rather is understood as an entirely isolated type of literacy. This is a myopic view of AI literacy, as AI literacy needs to be understood in the context of other types of literacy, in particular digital literacy. The model of compound and sequential digital exclusion (MCSDE) developed by van Deursen et al. (2017) postulates that one level of digital divides (such as lack of internet access) affects other levels of digital divides (such as lack of skills). This model would suggest that to fully understand a person’s AI literacy, an understanding of other inequalities is required such as their digital skill level and access to AI tools. This demands a more holistic view of AI literacy, where inequalities in AI literacy are embedded and compounded by other social and economic inequalities (Petrovčič et al., 2024).

The analysis also examined how the context of socioeconomic status (SES) and social inequality faced by participants factored into the studies’ consideration of AI literacy in the user group being studied. While a significant number (57, 44%) of studies considered some aspect of SES in their participants, this was primarily basic demographic data used to verify that the sample population matched the desired study group (36, 63% of papers coded for SES). An example of this is Kong et al.’s (2023, ID_095) study of the impact of an AI literacy course attended by exchange students at a Finnish university, which reported demographic information to describe the study population but only reported findings based on the participants as a single group. Another sizable group of authors (59, 46%) did not consider their participant’s lived context beyond a surface level examination in their analysis. When combined with studies that collect SES only for demographic purposes, this suggests that a majority of the studies captured in this scoping review do not consider how inequality impacts their research participants’ AI literacy.

An important finding was that only 10% (13) of total studies considered the impact of inequality in their participant’s AI literacy. Also, few of the studies captured (11, 9%) use theories of digital inequality or a critical framework in their research design. This reveals a significant research gap in how the field is being studied, by failing to consider the types of social inequality that might be shaping a participant’s AI literacy and how this might be exacerbating not just digital divides but social inequality. These findings were similar in the top four fields examined, suggesting that this research gap is an issue across disciplines.

We found that few studies include a form of reflection process in their study (8, 6%). Reflection refers to providing space in a study for participants to give input into the research design or research questions in an unscripted way. Participant reflection built into a study allows researchers to better capture the perspectives of the population they are studying, and personal reflexivity allows researchers to better understand the influence that power dynamics may have in their research findings (Flick, 2022). Adding reflection to studies about AI literacy is one way that researchers can produce knowledge on the topic that is more specific and nuanced.

Finally, the reported geographic location of where each study took place was analyzed, showing a bias to research conducted in three regions: Asia (29%), Europe (29%), and North America (22%). Few studies were captured from Africa and Central and South America and the Caribbean (2%, respectively) and no studies were captured from Oceania or the Middle East. The aim of coding for geography was to map where AI literacy is being constructed as a field of research; however, these patterns should be interpreted with caution and through a critical lens. UNESCO (2021) highlights that disparities in research production are shaped by structural conditions, including uneven investment, institutional and infrastructural capacity, and unequal access to global publishing networks. Global disparities in AI literacy research may also reflect asymmetries in how regions are positioned within the AI ecosystem. In regions such as North America, individuals are more likely to be positioned as users, educators, or developers of AI systems, supported by greater access to tools, infrastructure, and governmental investment, while other regions are more often positioned within the ecosystem through data generation, labour, and resource extraction (Birhane, 2019; Crawford, 2021). Similarly, research that investigates within country geographic disparities often focuses on rural versus urban, as a key dimension of inequality in relation to AI. These patterns are also shaped by broader, systemic dynamics associated with the AI divide as well as institutional and national readiness (Iida et al., 2026).

At the same time, underrepresentation in the literature does not necessarily reflect less engagement with AI or AI literacy. Importantly, academic publications represent just one mechanism through which knowledge about AI literacy is produced and shared. As previously discussed, civil society organizations, community groups, and local initiatives may be engaging in these issues in ways that are not captured within indexed academic literature. Furthermore, the inclusion criteria protocol for this scoping review was limited to English-language publications, which privileges particular regions and conceptualizations of AI literacy (Fane & Wastl, 2023). As such, the reported distribution reflects inequalities in research visibility and the limits of the resources available to complete the scoping review as well as multilingual limitations of the research team, rather than an account of global engagement with AI literacy research per se.

Reported geographic locations of studies

Composition of studies with no geographic location:				
 Experts on a topic 10%, (n=2)				

Some studies did not report a geographic location (21, 16%), which were typically those that were conducted online with participants from multiple regions (5, 24% of results with no geographic location) or where geographic location was not considered, such as works reviewing existing literature (9, 43%), engaging with online communities (5, 24%), or studies targeting experts on a topic (2, 10%). The lack of a systematic approach to incorporating geographical contexts limits the ability to account for how different cultural, social, and regional contexts shape experiences and understandings of AI literacy. Incorporating geographic context more systematically will be critical for supporting context-sensitive and globally relevant approaches to AI literacy research.

5. Discipline and setting

Each study was examined based on the academic discipline that it was situated in. The discipline was identified based on the primary field of the research, with the most common being education, computer science, engineering, social science, communication, and media studies. Those with authors originating from multiple disciplines or those that straddled multiple fields were coded as interdisciplinary (17, 13%). For example, Archambault (2024, ID_111) develops a framework for teaching AI literacy which applied concepts from both the education and library and information science fields. Of studies which primarily focused on one academic discipline, the education field is the most prolific in examining AI literacy (47, 36%). The studies we captured examined K-12 and university populations in roughly equal proportion, with around 40% (19 of 47) examining the AI literacy of K-12 students and/or teachers and around 45% (21 of 47) examining the AI literacy of post-secondary students and/or instructors. Of those studies situated in an educational context, Asia represents the largest region of included studies (20 of 47, 43%), with most of those studies occurring in China or Hong Kong.

A closer examination of the setting of each study shows that studying AI literacy through an educational lens is not limited to those in the education field, as most of the studies that occurred in a specific place (such as a classroom, workplace, or healthcare setting) occurred in educational spaces (60, 47%). Two examples of studies taking place in educational settings outside the educational context are Koenig's (2020, ID_102) interdisciplinary study of post-secondary student's algorithmic literacy via journaling in a writing class, as well as Knoth et al.'s (2024, ID_008) study of prompt engineering in LLM-based systems, which occurred in an educational setting only because it used post-secondary students as the sample to test the system. By comparison, studies taking place in either workplace (10, 8%) and healthcare settings (1, <1%) were rare, with only one study taking place in a healthcare setting. Similar to geographic location, some studies did not indicate a specific setting (58, 45%), such as those that studied online participants. The prevalence of the education field in our findings suggests that AI literacy studies are typically focused on classroom type settings and are used to assess literacy levels of students in order to inform content or teaching delivery mode. This suggests that AI literacy is seldom studied in the general population but rather the focus is on student populations in formal educational settings. There is a need to expand the focus of AI literacy to include more diverse populations, including older adults, parents, and the public at large.

Distribution of disciplines of AI literacy studies

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Studies from the social science, communication, and media studies fields made up the second largest group of studies included in the scoping review (35, 27%). Not surprisingly, half of the studies examining platforms in general or multiple platforms, (16 of 35, 46%) came from these disciplines, as well as most of the studies examining algorithms on TikTok and Facebook.

Geographically, this category looked different than the overall findings and the education field. Studies within these disciplines that included a geographic location took place in Europe (10 of 35, 29%), Asia (8 of 35, 23%), or North America (6 of 35, 17%), with a significant number of studies (11 of 35, 31%) taking place in either multiple regions or lacking a specific location. The final area of study that these fields differed from in comparison to the overall findings is the terminology employed in the studies. The majority of authors in the social science, communication, and media studies fields use algorithm awareness (22 of 35, 63%) and few use AI literacy (2 of 35, 6%) as their primary term. These findings show that within the larger field of AI literacy, some studies are using terms that are less common in the wider discourse due to disciplinary differences. This makes definitions particularly important and creates a need to explain in detail what a study is examining, rather than making assumptions about the meaning of terminology.

An unexpected finding is that few studies addressing AI literacy come from the disciplines of computer science and engineering (17, 13%). There are 11 additional studies that were coded as interdisciplinary, and co-written by computer science or engineering authors, published in computer science or engineering journals, or the study's sample included computer science or engineering students. Even with their inclusion, these fields (28) were less represented than the education field (47). This suggests that AI literacy is more frequently studied within fields concerned with learning, use, and social impact, than within those primarily focused on the development and implementation of AI technologies. While AI literacy is often framed as geared to non-experts (Mattias et al., 2023, ID_127), this does not imply that critical engagement with AI is unnecessary within technical fields; technical expertise does not inherently equate to a critical understanding of the social, ethical, and political dimensions of AI. From an AI ecosystem perspective, where all actors are interconnected, AI is a shared responsibility. If AI systems are to be safe and equitable, then critical AI literacy should be extended to the areas of design, development, and implementation and needs to be recognized as an important area of research across all disciplines.

6. Outcomes and Recommendations

We examined the types of outcomes and related recommendations presented in each study to understand how authors frame the implications of their work and identify directions for future research. In this analysis, we distinguish between outcomes, which refer to the reported impacts or contributions of a study itself, and recommendations, which refer to the actions or directions authors propose based on their findings.

We analyzed the types of outcomes reported across studies to understand how AI literacy research is positioned in relation to its intended impacts. Outcomes were grouped into four broad categories: 1) outcomes that are learning-oriented, i.e., they influence the learning/awareness of the specific group under study; 2) outcomes that are economic, i.e., they focus on economic benefits; 3) outcomes that are social or ethical, i.e., they address specific social factors, including addressing social inequality; and 4) finally outcomes that are technological, i.e., they address how technology can be better used or designed to impact AI literacy or awareness.

Learning-orientated outcomes were the most common, accounting for 57% of studies (74 of 129). This is unsurprising, given the purpose and disciplinary focus of the studies included in the scoping review, the majority of which examine AI literacy within educational or user-focused contexts. These studies primarily aimed to improve awareness or understanding among their specific studied populations. For example, Ng et al. (2023_ID_021) develop and validate an AI literacy questionnaire tailored to student populations, as a result of their previous research with secondary students. A further 29% of studies (38 of 129) reported social or ethical outcomes, addressing factors such as public understanding of AI impacts, or, in some cases, issues of social inequality. For example, Archambault et al. (2024_ID_060) describe workshops designed to engage students with the social implications of AI technologies. By contrast, technological outcomes were less common (12%, 16 of 129), and economic outcomes were rarely examined (4%, 5 of 129). An example of an economic outcome comes from Nguyen et al. (2024, ID_72), whose study on financial technology (fintech), found that three dimensions of fintech literacy, namely blockchain literacy, crowdfunding literacy, and AI literacy, directly affected digital entrepreneurial intention. Even with this economic framing, the focus of the study remains on individual economic benefit, and not on the economics of the AI ecosystem in a structural way. The category of outcomes that studies fall under suggests that AI literacy research is primarily oriented towards improving the awareness and skills of user groups, rather than toward engaging with the systems, infrastructure, and conditions that shape the AI ecosystem as a whole.

Distribution of reported outcomes

Distribution of reported recommendations

Building on the analysis of reported outcomes, we examined the recommendations presented in each study to understand how authors propose to act on these findings, and how they may situate their research within the broader field of AI literacy. The most common recommendation was the need for further research (45%, 60 of 129), with authors identifying areas for deeper investigation, addressing gaps revealed by the study, or extending the scope of their own work. A further 27% (34 of 129) provided broad or general recommendations to improve AI literacy or technological understandings, while only 22% (29 of 129) offered more specific recommendations related to training, pedagogy, or skill development. Finally, there is a small group of studies (6 of 129, 5%) which provides other types of recommendations such as how to improve on existing theoretical models (Hu & Wang, 2023, ID_071; Liu et al., 2024, ID_106), ways to explore broad conceptual ideas (Das, 2024, ID_038; Tsao & Nogues, 2024, ID_031), and some studies included multiple recommendation types (Silva et al., 2024, ID_070; Swart, 2021, ID_066). The predominance of recommendations for further research suggests that the field of AI literacy research is still in its infancy. While longitudinal studies are only just beginning to emerge, there is a growing recognition for a need for sustained and long-term research in this area. A longitudinal design allows researchers to track changes in AI literacy and inequalities, measure shifts in public awareness and agency (Felaco, 2024), and provide policymakers with an evidence base that evolves over time. Human-centred governance calls for “a shift towards mixed-method, longitudinal research that captures how people interact with AI in real-world settings, including how they adopt, adapt, or resist technology” (Pi et al., 2025, p. 10.). Longitudinal research is necessary to situate AI literacy research not as a static field, but as an ever-evolving field within a dynamic AI ecosystem.

Most notably, policy-oriented recommendations were rare, with only a marginal number of studies (3 of 129, 2%) referencing systemic-level interventions, such as policy development, legal dimensions, or algorithmic audits. This limited engagement with policy and regulatory approaches suggests that AI literacy research is largely disconnected from broader governance processes. The absence of policy-oriented recommendations in particular is significant given the understanding that many of the risks and harms associated with AI cannot be addressed through individual awareness or education alone (Noble, 2018; Rovatsos et al., 2019).

**Policy-oriented:
2%**

The limited presence of such recommendations indicates that AI literacy research remains largely oriented towards individual or group capacity building, rather than engaging in the conditions that produce and sustain social inequalities within the AI ecosystem. If left unaddressed, AI literacy studies will lack the institutional leverage to meaningfully inform policy.

KEY FINDINGS

Each of the six themes discussed in the results section offers important insights. By also examining the intersection of the six themes, we were able to discern how they intersect and what broader patterns emerge across the themes. This analysis revealed three key findings. Together, these findings point to systemic challenges that constrain the development of more coordinated, equitable, and trusted approaches to the development of AI literacy that help inform educational approaches as well as AI governance, regulation, and policy.

1 Fragmentation slows collective progress in AI literacy

There is no consensus on a definition of AI literacy. This creates challenges in comparing AI literacy interventions across contexts. Disciplinary silos prevent the development of shared definitions, scales, and cross-sectoral frameworks linking AI literacy to governance or policy.

- Nearly half of the studies analyzed use AI literacy as the primary term, while others rely on terms such as algorithmic awareness or use different terminology entirely. This lack of clarity makes it difficult to compare findings or track AI literacy across time, populations, and sectors.
- Most studies describe AI in general terms rather than specific AI applications. As a result, research overlooks how people interact with AI in real-life settings. There is a need for a refocus from AI as a closed black-box to the AI ecosystem, that encompasses the many facets that shape AI.
- Research remains siloed across disciplines and geographies. A large share of studies come from education and social science, with few contributions from computer science, engineering or interdisciplinary perspectives. Very few studies validate their findings across cultural or national contexts, limiting the development of shared standards.

2

Narrow focus on technocentric skills over critical engagement

AI literacy studies focus on technical understandings and competencies with AI, while overlooking the need for critical evaluation with a focus on societal impacts and underlying techno-political systems. The emphasis on individual learning obscures questions of power, consent, and user agency, reducing AI literacy to a technical capacity.

- Most research tools assess knowledge about and misconceptions of AI technologies rather than fostering critical engagement. The problem is that this establishes an incomplete baseline that precludes the development of holistic AI literacy interventions.
- Most studies frame AI literacy as an individual competency, with the majority defining it narrowly as knowledge, skills, or attitudes. Only a few expand the scope to include beyond basic awareness of AI, yet without sufficiently considering decision-making, collective experience or user agency.
- When user agency is addressed, studies equate it with the ability to use AI tools, rather than with the capacity to resist or refuse, treating non-participation as illiteracy, rather than informed choice.

3

Limited attention to social inequality and lived experience

AI literacy is rarely examined in relation to social inequality. This omission presumes universal participation and equal access, overlooking how structural conditions shape people's access to and use of AI, as well as how they understand, evaluate, and challenge it.

- Key factors of social inequality are overlooked in the studies, creating a limited picture of AI literacy in society and existing digital divides.
- AI literacy is studied mostly in the classroom rather than in real-life contexts. This limits the understanding of urban, civic, workplace, or community contexts.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following implications and recommendations are directed towards governments, researchers, educators (e.g., K-12, colleges, and higher-ed), public institutions, international organizations, non-profit organizations, and other stakeholders involved in shaping how AI systems are developed, governed, implemented, and understood across society. An interconnected AI ecosystem emphasises that responsibility for AI literacy is shared across sectors, rather than residing in any one field or organization. Effective AI literacy policy must be multifaceted to address the diverse ways AI is encountered in everyday life.

Implication: **Conceptual fragmentation limits the comparability and scalability of AI literacy research**

AI literacy research currently lacks conceptual convergence across disciplines, sectors, and contexts. Definitions vary substantially between studies, and terminology is often used inconsistently, including within a single study. This fragmentation creates challenges for AI literacy practice, cohesive policy development, and AI governance and regulation. At the same time, the diversity of approaches to understand and measure AI literacy reflects the reality of how AI systems are encountered differently across communities, institutions, cultures, and other social contexts.

Recommendation: **Greater conceptual convergence is needed to support coordination across AI literacy research, policy, and practice**

Stakeholders need to work towards greater conceptual convergence in AI literacy through the development of shared frameworks, adaptable assessment approaches, and cross-sector dialogue. Efforts should support collaborations, benchmarking, and evidence-informed policy while remaining responsive to contextual needs and the evolving understanding of AI systems.

Universalized literacy frameworks can privilege dominant cultural assumptions, institutional priorities, and ways of knowing while marginalizing local, Indigenous, community-based, or non-Western forms of knowledge and participation (Perry, 2021; Shank Lauwo, 2025). Standardized models may reproduce colonial assumptions by positioning certain forms of subject expertise, language, or engagement as neutral and universally applicable (Lomellini & Lowenthal, 2025).

Rather than imposing a single universal model of AI literacy, the findings suggest the need for flexible, domain-based frameworks that recognize how AI systems operate differently across sectors, institutions, and everyday experiences. While some degree of shared structure is necessary, overly standardized approaches risk reproducing existing social inequalities.

Domain-based approaches offer a possible alternative. They establish shared foundation areas that can support coordination across contexts while allowing interoperable flexibility in implementation and localization. Emerging initiatives such as the drafted Media and Artificial Literacy (MAIL) framework by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) provides one example of this direction (OECD, 2026). The framework identifies five broad domains: i) reflect and act ethically and responsibly, ii) access and use, iii) analyze and evaluate, iv) participate and collaborate, and v) create. As an interdisciplinary and international framework, it demonstrates the potential for shared conceptual domains that support coordination while still leaving room for diverse contextual adaptations.

2

Implication: **Narrow competency-based approaches limit the transformative potential of AI literacy**

AI literacy studies focus on technical understanding and competence with AI, while overlooking the need for critical evaluation with a focus on societal impacts and underlying techno-political systems. The emphasis on individual learning obscures questions of power, consent, and user agency, reducing AI literacy to a technical competency. Current AI literacy approaches have been developed primarily from educational contexts. Frameworks for AI literacy should move beyond focusing on skills and competencies by integrating lived experience and social context. Through this critical lens, technologies are never neutral and interventions must account for the full conditions of people's lives.

Recommendation: **AI literacy must be critical and understood within the broader AI ecosystem**

Many AI literacy studies continue to focus primarily on individual competencies such as technical knowledge, individual understanding, or functional awareness. While these skills are important, narrow competency-based approaches risk framing AI literacy as an individualized responsibility. This can limit the transformative potential of AI literacy by assuming that individuals adapt to AI systems instead of addressing the systemic, institutional, and governance structures that shape how these systems operate and impact communities differently.

Understanding AI within the broader AI ecosystem recognizes AI as a sociotechnical system shaped by symbiotic social, economic, and political, and technological relationships (Livingstone, 2004; Pedreschi et al., 2023). This necessitates a shift from functional AI literacy to critical AI literacy (Veldhuis, 2024) that includes understanding how AI systems are developed, governed, deployed, financed, regulated, and contested, as well as how power influences whose interests are prioritized, whose data is extracted, and who experiences harms and benefits (Crawford, 2021; Noble, 2018). Stakeholders should ensure that an assessment of how inequalities shape the public's interactions with AI is integrated into AI literacy interventions. Through this critical lens, technologies are never neutral and interventions must account for the full conditions of people's lives. This includes assessment and policy mechanisms recognizing the vital importance of an informed public, the right to informed refusal, the need for people to exercise agency, and cross-sector transparency.

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Implication:
AI literacy research requires broader recognition of diverse forms of knowledge, expertise, and experience

The need for greater conceptual convergence alongside critical and ecosystem-based approaches to AI literacy points to the limitations of relying primarily on academic perspectives and methodologies. The scoping review findings suggest that the priorities of current research continue to center assessment and measurement as well as instructional outcomes, while broader questions of lived experience, social context, and collective responses to AI ecosystems receive limited attention. By contrast, civil society initiatives foreground these dimensions through work that combines research, public engagement, and community-grounded approaches. Their work highlights a disconnect between what is currently prioritized within the academic field and the concerns being actively explored and addressed within community contexts.

The limited use of participatory and reflexive methodologies can reinforce technocratic approaches that narrowly position the public as solely users of AI systems rather than also democratic participants within the broader AI ecosystem.

Recommendation:
Future AI literacy research and reviews should incorporate grey literature, community-based initiatives, and participatory forms of knowledge

Although this review provides an important starting point, meaningful AI literacy knowledge consolidation cannot end with formal literature alone. Future knowledge synthesis of AI literacy needs to expand beyond peer-reviewed research to include grey literature, community-based initiatives, practitioner expertise, public projects, policy reports, civil society work, and interdisciplinary collaborations. Incorporating grey literature is important because it may reduce publication bias, improve comprehensiveness, and provide a more balanced understanding of the evidence (Paez, 2017). However, grey literature often remains underrepresented within systematic and scoping reviews due to the limited accessibility, inconsistent indexing, and the lack of standardized guidance for incorporating these materials within inclusion protocols (Khalil et al., 2026).

If AI literacy research is to contribute meaningfully to democratic AI governance and policy development, then the evidence base informing that work must also reflect democratic, participatory, and community-engaged approaches to knowledge production. Future work should give greater attention to methodologies such as co-design, member checking (or participant validation), research creation, collaborative facilitation, and community validation processes. Greater recognition and use of these approaches would help position participants and communities as active contributors to AI literacy knowledge rather than passive subjects of study. In doing so, AI literacy research may become better equipped to support public agency, democratic participation in civic life, and community-centred responses to the rapid evolution of the AI ecosystems.

Transformative Impact

Strengthened public and civil society capacity to critically engage within the AI ecosystem and contribute meaningfully to democratic AI governance.

The United Nations Education, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2021) warns that AI governance represents one of the most critical global challenges of our time. There is a need for participatory and community-centered approaches to AI literacy. Framing AI literacy as an individual responsibility deflects attention from the structural reforms required for algorithmic accountability. Responsible design includes enabling the public to understand and, when necessary, challenge algorithmic systems and environments. Advancing this work will require research and consultation that bridges academic, civic, and community perspectives to fully capture the power dynamics, digital marginalization, and lived experiences that current approaches overlook.

Although Libraries and non-government organizations (NGOs) have played a recognised role in contributing to literacy development, their role in AI literacy is to date not sufficiently central. AI literacy policy should support the efforts of existing trusted institutions like libraries and community groups to develop AI literacy at scale (Anderson et al., 2025). Public libraries are among the few public institutions with both the infrastructure and mandate to provide space to diverse publics around complex issues such as algorithmic bias, disinformation, and surveillance (Audunson et al., 2019; Hall, 2010; Jaeger et al., 2013; Panzarella, 2020). Libraries can act as “democratic canaries” because they register and absorb the pressures of inequality, technological disruption, and social division (Hanell et al., 2025). Their continued vitality despite vast changes in recent decades to how the public consumes information and the accompanying misleading prediction of obsolescence demonstrates their enduring role in literacy, inclusion, and public trust (Huang et al., 2024).

Support for cross-sector capacity building would allow policymakers and stakeholders to contextualize AI impacts locally and empower residents. AI literacy policy that does not centre these institutions will struggle to achieve scale, equity, or public trust. Sustained investment in libraries, NGOs, and community groups as critical AI literacy mediators is foundational to effective and accountable AI literacy governance. While educational institutions like schools, colleges, and universities serve a role in strengthening AI literacy, they are limited in the social groups they reach. Transformative critical AI literacy creates the possibility for all communities not only to navigate the AI ecosystem, but to reimagine, demand, and build more equitable technological futures.

CONCLUSION

We need to embed critical AI literacy across all AI literacy frameworks and interventions by integrating lived experience, social context, and explicit attention to the broader AI ecosystem, including questions of power, inequality, user agency, and the right to informed refusal.

What is AI literacy?

AI literacy can be situated at the intersection of other types of literacy such as media literacy and digital literacy, but the concept is distinct. What complicates our understanding of AI literacy is that AI is highly opaque and black-box, creating obstacles to grasping what these systems are doing and how (Burrell, 2016; Petrovčič, et al. 2024). This requires an interdisciplinary effort in conceptualizing and mapping AI literacy. Based on our analyses of the current literature, we see five different types of conceptualizations of AI literacy:

1. **Competency-based approaches:** focused on skills, knowledge, and ethical use of AI.
2. **Awareness-oriented approaches:** centered on recognizing the presence and influence of AI or algorithms on everyday life.
3. **Technical approaches:** emphasizing programming, system design, or operational understandings.
4. **Critical or sociotechnical approaches:** focused on power, inequality, governance, and resistance.
5. **Specialized frameworks:** tailored to particular professions, sectors, or use cases.

We also identified several limitations. Often these approaches make the assumption that individuals are voluntarily engaging with AI rather than being subjected to AI. We found that the majority of studies on AI literacy build on this assumption and aim to strengthen individual skill development, moving attention away from collective resistance strategies, structural reforms, and institutional accountability. There is a need for more studies that conceptualize AI literacy based on the critical or sociotechnical approaches and we stress the need for critical AI literacy. Research needs to continue examining how AI literacy is conceptualized across disciplines, regions, and stakeholders, as how we define AI literacy influences what individuals and communities learn and how they can engage with AI systems locally and globally.

Furthermore, we found that how AI is conceptualized directly shapes how AI literacy is understood. Definitions that focus narrowly on the technical aspects of AI risk overlooking the broader systemic influences on AI development, deployment, governance, and experience. Future studies should therefore adopt the term *AI ecosystem*, rather than relying on use of the terms AI or AI technologies. This language emphasizes the sociotechnical nature of AI, seeing AI as interactively shaped by symbiotic social, economic, political, and technological relationships (Livingstone, 2004; Pedreschi, 2023).

AI literacy matters in society

There is an urgent need to include public voices in policy and deployment decisions that shape how people live. It is essential to balance technical AI advances with public trust and shared values, so that AI governance retains sustainable legitimacy into the future (Coeckelbergh, 2025; Duarte & Garcia, 2024; Gilman, 2023; Ter-Minassian, 2025). We and AI (2026), a UK nonprofit states: “Critical AI literacy has never been more important. We are a non-profit organisation working to encourage, enable, and empower critical thinking about AI. We aim to help more people make informed decisions about how they live with AI.” AI literacy is increasingly recognized by academic institutions and nonprofit organizations as a critical area of focus.

Several motivations drive this growing interest. One major reason is the need to prepare the future workforce with the skills required to effectively integrate AI into professional environments. If children are exposed to the AI ecosystem early in educational settings, they can learn AI skills that can later translate not only in their educational choices but also in assuring job readiness. This perspective was particularly prominent in Asia, where many of the studies we reviewed examined the implementation of interventions to strengthen AI literacy in students and teachers. Yet another key motivation for focusing on AI literacy is to increase diversity in AI development and implementation to ensure that AI systems reflect and serve a broad range of communities and perspectives. This has been a major issue in AI development, and has been recognized as an urgent problem.

Another important motivation is the reduction of barriers to participation in AI governance and regulation. As AI plays a growing role in spreading disinformation through deepfakes, biased algorithms, and other forms of manipulation, AI literacy can help individuals critically evaluate information and protect themselves from misuse. To create a shared vision for the future of AI and its role in everyday life, people need accessible opportunities to engage in these conversations. Strengthening the public's AI literacy can encourage inclusive participation and decision-making.

Approaches to the study of AI literacy

The education system already focuses on media and digital literacy and has now also come to play a critically important role in strengthening AI literacy. Many of the studies assess students' and teachers' AI literacy and develop interventions to improve AI literacy. There is a need to expand AI literacy beyond schools and universities into communities. The majority of the studies reviewed utilized quantitative methods, often relying on survey and self-report measures. However, it is important to consider literacy as an active skill occurring in specific socio-economic contexts, not something that is acquired by people passively in a neutral environment. This has been extensively explored by library and information science scholars, who define information literacy as a situated practice enabling people to question dominant ideologies and imagine alternatives (Elmborg, 2006). To better understand how AI is being used by a range of social groups and what challenges and concerns arise, qualitative methods such as interviews, observations and ethnographies are needed. We call for an expansion of methodological approaches to the study of AI literacy that are more in-situ and attuned to the needs to individuals and communities.

Strengthening critical AI literacy

Despite the recognition of the importance of AI literacy, it remains unclear how to develop interventions to strengthen it. One challenge is conceptualizing what AI literacy is. Better conceptualizations could help scale AI literacy not only across populations (k-12 to high school to older adults) but also across contexts (rural vs urban). To develop greater conceptual consistency more engagement is needed across disciplinary silos, types of institutions (academic, non-profit, government). A second challenge is the narrow focus on technological competencies rather than critical engagement. We advocate for a multifactorial approach to AI literacy, one that also includes critical AI literacy as a key dimension. Third, AI literacy interventions need to be culturally sensitive and targeted to the needs of different settings and populations.

In conclusion, AI literacy is a broad term used in different disciplines to achieve different objectives. But overall, there is agreement of its societal relevance. We advocate for closer collaborations between academic scholars from different disciplines as well as with non-profit organizations to bridge the current disconnect between understandings of AI literacy as capacity building with those that see it as a tool to advocate and resist. We need to shift toward a focus on critical AI literacy which highlights the need to understand how AI is developed, governed, deployed, financed, regulated, and contested, as well as how power influences whose interests are prioritized, whose data is extracted, and who experiences harms and benefits. There is much synergy in the current work, and collaborations can broaden understandings of critical AI literacy and support the effort to prepare the public to engage fully and critically with the AI ecosystem.

KNOWLEDGE MOBILIZATION ACTIVITIES AND IMPACT

Knowledge mobilization was a key goal, as our findings inform current debates in Canada and UK about the role of AI literacy in informing governance and democracy. The current work is also relevant to policy think-tanks to further understand current trends and gaps and their role in strengthening AI literacy and critical engagement with AI and its social and economic impacts. We engaged stakeholders through a variety of activities, taking into consideration their different information needs. We also outline a plan for next steps in knowledge mobilization and the need for future research projects to fill the gaps identified in the scoping review.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

We engaged with four key stakeholders in Canada and UK. In the UK, we engaged with Tim Davies of Connected By Data and Tania Duarte of We And AI. In Canada, we engaged with Dr. Kara Brisson-Boivin of MediaSmarts and with two public libraries, Shawn Mitchell from the Toronto Public Library (TPL) and Michael Ciccone from the London Public Library (LPL), Ontario. The period of engagement consisted of meetings to discuss the needs of stakeholders, discussions around definitions of AI literacy, consideration of ways to engage in deeper conversation around the topic, and reflection on how to impact government policy; this engagement took place over four months during the knowledge mobilisation phase of the project. We also devised a plan to reach the general public and additional stakeholders such as K-12 teachers and librarians, with the aim of creating permanent, open access resources.

We organized two panels to convene digital advocacy organizations, public bodies, and researchers for a public talk and research panel that addressed the emerging role of AI literacy and the implications for digital inclusion. By organizing the talk online, we were able to invite advocacy organizations and NGOs from both Canada and UK, as well as invite scholars and the public from both countries. The first panel was organized at the Faculty of Information and Media Studies (FIMS), Western University, London, ON, Canada, and brought together four experts from community organizations.

We also engaged with library practitioners and presented preliminary findings of our work at two events that brings together practitioners and academics:

Virtual Poster: Anderson, H., Quan-Haase, A., Maeda, T., Gignac, S., Willis, K. (2025, June). The role of librarians in improving AI literacy and awareness. In Generative AI in Libraries (GAIL) Conference 2025.

Virtual Poster: Maeda, T., Quan-Haase, A., Willis, K., Anderson, H., & Gignac, S. (2025, Dec.). Toward agency-centered AI literacy. ASIS&T Annual Meeting, Washington, DC.

WHY CRITICAL AI LITERACY MATTERS:

Implications for policy and practice in UK and Canada

Purpose

To convene digital advocacy organizations, public bodies and researchers for a public talk and research panel that explores the emerging role of critical AI literacy and the implications for digital divides.

November 10th, 2025

Description

We will convene some leading organizations and advocates to discuss the role of critical AI literacy in both UK and Canada. We aim to enable knowledge transfer with the stakeholders who can address the implications of this and implement changes at a policy level in UK and Canada – through new practices in cities through NGOs and activists who work with AI policy change.

SPEAKERS

Co-Chairs of event

Drs. Anabel Quan-Haase and Katharine Willis

Experts

- Tim Davies, Connected by Data, UK <https://connectedbydata.org/>
Connected by Data campaign to put community at the centre of data narratives, practices and policies by advocating for collective and open data governance
- Dr. Kara Brisson-Boivin, MediaSmarts, Canada
MediaSmarts has been developing digital media literacy programs and resources for Canadian homes, schools and communities since 1996.
- Tania Duarte, We and AI, UK <https://weandai.org/>
We and AI are a non-profit organisation working to encourage, enable, and empower critical thinking about AI.
- Shawn Mitchell, Toronto Public Library, Canada <https://tpl.ca/>
Toronto Public Library is one of the largest public libraries in Canada, and has developed an AI policy.

The panel discussion was recorded and made available through Western's YouTube channel

EXPERT PANELS

AI, INTIMACY, AND INFLUENCE:

Youth, parasocial relationships, and the AI age

Purpose

To convene researchers for a public talk and research panel during Media Literacy Week 2025 that explores the emerging dynamics of parasocial relationships between youth and AI-powered technologies, including chatbots, avatars, influencers, and recommendation systems.

October 30th, 2025

Description

During the 20th annual Media Literacy Week (October 27-31, 2025), MediaSmarts, in partnership with the Internet, Technology, and Digital Sociology research cluster of the CSA and FIMS, will host a panel event that examines young people's parasocial relationships with AI and their implications for media literacy education and policy in Canada. In partnership with MediaSmarts and The Internet, Technology, and Digital Sociology Cluster of the Canadian Sociological Association (CSA)

SPEAKERS

Chair of event

Dr. Michael Adorjan

Experts

- Dr. Anabel Quan-Haase, Professor, Sociology and Information and Media Studies, Western University.
- Takuya Maeda, PhD Student, Information and Media Studies, Western University.
- Dr. Celeste Campos-Castillo, Associate Professor, Media and Information, Michigan State University
- Dr. Yuxing Zhang (Yolanda), An Wang Postdoctoral Fellow, Fairbank Center for Chinese Studies, Harvard University.

The panel discussion was recorded and made available through MediaSmart's YouTube channel

POLICY STAKEHOLDERS

During the duration of the KSG, we worked closely with policy stakeholders. We shared our Executive Summary Report with the four organizations involved in the project who engage in advocacy and policy development around AI literacy. To ensure that the project's findings were relevant to stakeholders and the implications clearly articulated, we shared the KSG policy brief with each stakeholder for consultation, requesting feedback and input and met with them to discuss suggested changes. As part of this close collaboration, we were invited to be signatories to open letters forwarded to the UK and Canadian governments.

Open Letter to the UK Government—Prioritising AI Literacy for All Citizens

<https://connectedbydata.org/blog/2025/07/08/open-letter-ai-literacy-for-all>

Response: <https://connectedbydata.org/blog/2025/09/18/ai-literacy-letter-reply>

Open Letter to the Canadian Government—MediaSmarts Calls on Federal Government to Act on National Digital Media Literacy Strategy

Open Letter Canada: <https://mediasmarts.ca/about-us/press-centre/mediasmarts-calls-federal-government-act-national-digital-media-literacy-strategy>

ACADEMIC KNOWLEDGE USERS

The final report will be presented to diverse groups of academics and stakeholders during the Knowledge Synthesis Forum on May 6, co-hosted by the Social Science and Humanities Research Council of Canada (SSHRC) and the UK Research and Innovation's Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) and Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC). The forum will allow to not only for the dissemination of the findings to key academic groups and stakeholder audiences but will also provide an opportunity for discussion and deeper engagement. The findings of the scoping review have been shared with diverse academic groups through presentations, posters, and publications.

The academic publications, conference presentations, invited talks, and keynote presentations contribute to the body of knowledge on the importance of developing solid understandings of AI literacy and the range of interventions available.

Hanna Barakat
& Archival
Images of AI +
AIxDESIGN /
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ommons.org/lice
nses/by/4.0/)

ACADEMIC KNOWLEDGE USERS

Type of output	Details
Presentation	Willis, K., Groek, E. and Amro, I. (2026). Urban AI and deep borders. Re-thinking (Critical) Digital Geopolitics workshop at Royal Geographical Society/IGB annual conference, London, August 2026.
Publication	Maeda, T., Quan-Haase, A., Willis, K., Anderson, H., & Gignac, S. (2025). Toward agency-centered AI literacy. In Proceedings of the ASIS&T Annual Meeting, The Role of Information Science in the Age of AI. Washington, DC. https://asistdl.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/pr2.1472
Invited Speaker	Quan-Haase, A. (January 27, 2026). Digital literacy in a changing digital world. Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong.
Invited Speaker	Quan-Haase, A. (December 8, 2025). "Critical AI literacy in youth." Journée d'études IA, plateformes numériques, travail et jeunesse, À l'Institut national de la recherche scientifique (INRS). Quebec City, QC.
Keynote	Quan-Haase, A. & Maeda, T. (August 7, 2025). "AI literacy, inequality and ethics: Anthropomorphism and parasociality in affective design". CITAMS Media Sociology Symposium , American Sociological Association.
Invited Panelist	Quan-Haase, A., Komp-Leukkunen, K., Baysal, B. & Miltsov, A. (April 9, 2026). GenAI and the future of work. Department of Sociology, Bishop University. Sherbrook, QC.
Book Chapter	Maeda, T., Quan-Haase, A., Nau, C., & Fofah, K. (in press). Ethics in CSS and AI. In M. Haim & E. Domahidi (eds.), Handbook of computational communication research (2nd ed). Routledge.

FUTURE MOBILIZATION

The research agenda initiated as part of this KSG grant will continue in close collaboration with stakeholders and academic partners through future grants and projects. In addition to the already conducted activities, we also plan the following initiatives to disseminate key findings and implications with diverse academic groups and non-academic stakeholders including community groups and policy-makers:

- publication of the AI literacy scoping review in a peer-reviewed journal;
- conference presentations of the AI literacy scoping review;
- publish and share KSG policy brief and final report through social media and public web sites;
- participate in stakeholder engagement through panels and talks; and finally
- dissemination of the findings through media releases.

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We have chosen to use images from the Better Images of AI project. Coordinated by We and AI, this initiative brings together academics, artists, advocates, and non-profit organizations to develop more socially informed visual representations of AI technologies and their impacts.

We encourage other researchers, educators, organizations, and institutions to adopt more representative and context-sensitive visual language when communicating about AI.

Find out more here: <https://betterimagesofai.org/>

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